

Comparative Study to Evaluate the Clinical Efficacy and Safety of Isobaric Levobupivacaine in Lower Limb Orthopaedic Surgeries

Nitin Kumar¹, Priyanka Singh², Sukesh Kumar³, Sudama Prasad⁴

¹Ex Senior Resident, Department of Anaesthesiology, Indira Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences, Patna, Bihar, India

²Ex Senior Resident, Department of Anaesthesiology, Rajendra Institute of Medical Sciences, Ranchi, Jharkhand, India

³Assistant Professor, Department of Anaesthesiology, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

⁴Professor & HOD, Department of Anaesthesiology, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 25-03-2024 / Revised: 23-04-2024 / Accepted: 25-05-2024

Corresponding Author: Priyanka Singh

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Local anesthetics are essential in regional anesthesia for orthopedic surgeries, offering pain management and motor blockade. Levobupivacaine, the S-enantiomer of bupivacaine, is suggested to have a safer profile with fewer adverse effects. The purpose of this study was to compare the clinical effectiveness and safety of isobaric levobupivacaine vs hyperbaric bupivacaine in lower limb orthopaedic procedures.

Methods: A hundred patients were randomly randomised to receive either hyperbaric bupivacaine or isobaric levobupivacaine during their elective lower limb orthopaedic operations. Adverse events, postoperative pain levels, the beginning and duration of sensory and motor blockade, and intraoperative haemodynamic parameters were also noted. The statistical analysis was done with SPSS 23.0.

Results: The onset of sensory blockade was faster in the hyperbaric bupivacaine group (6.8 ± 1.0 minutes) compared to the isobaric levobupivacaine group (8.5 ± 1.2 minutes, $p < 0.001$). However, the duration of sensory (210.4 ± 18.7 minutes) and motor blockade (180.5 ± 15.6 minutes) was longer with isobaric levobupivacaine compared to hyperbaric bupivacaine (sensory: 195.2 ± 16.9 minutes, motor: 165.7 ± 14.8 minutes; $p = 0.002$ and $p = 0.001$, respectively). Postoperative pain scores were significantly lower in the isobaric levobupivacaine group at 1 hour, 4 hours, and 12 hours post-surgery ($p < 0.001$). The incidence of adverse events was similar between the groups.

Conclusion: Isobaric levobupivacaine provides a longer duration of sensory and motor blockade and superior postoperative pain control compared to hyperbaric bupivacaine, with a comparable safety profile. These findings suggest that isobaric levobupivacaine may be preferable for surgeries requiring extended anesthesia and postoperative pain management.

Recommendations: It is advised that more research to be done with broader sample sizes and a more varied population in order to validate these results and investigate long-term effects.

Keywords: Isobaric Levobupivacaine, Hyperbaric Bupivacaine, Lower Limb Orthopaedic Surgeries, Regional Anesthesia, Postoperative Pain Management.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Local anesthetics are a cornerstone of regional anesthesia, particularly in orthopaedic surgeries where effective pain management and motor blockade are crucial for surgical success and patient comfort. Among the various local anesthetics, bupivacaine has been widely used due to its potent anesthetic and analgesic properties. However, the development of levobupivacaine, the S-enantiomer of bupivacaine, has introduced a potentially safer alternative with fewer cardiotoxic and neurotoxic effects [1].

Levobupivacaine, being an isobaric solution, has demonstrated clinical advantages in various studies. Its isobaric nature allows it to provide a consistent spread of anesthesia, reducing the variability seen with hyperbaric solutions, which are influenced by patient positioning and other factors [2]. On the other hand, hyperbaric bupivacaine remains a popular choice due to its predictable onset and denser block, which can be advantageous in certain surgical settings.

Lower limb orthopedic surgeries, such as total knee arthroplasty, hip arthroplasty, and fracture repairs, require effective regional anesthesia to ensure pain control and facilitate early mobilization. Effective anesthesia not only improves surgical conditions but also enhances postoperative recovery by reducing the need for systemic analgesics, which can have significant side effects [3]. Therefore, comparing the efficacy and safety profiles of isobaric levobupivacaine and hyperbaric bupivacaine is essential to optimize anesthetic practice in these procedures.

Previous research has indicated that isobaric levobupivacaine provides prolonged sensory and motor blockade with a lower risk of adverse cardiovascular and central nervous system effects compared to racemic bupivacaine [4]. However, studies comparing it directly with hyperbaric bupivacaine in the context of lower limb orthopaedic surgeries are limited. The current literature suggests that while hyperbaric bupivacaine offers a rapid onset of action and a reliable block profile, the duration of anesthesia and postoperative analgesia might be superior with isobaric levobupivacaine [5].

This study aimed at evaluating the clinical efficacy and safety of isobaric levobupivacaine versus hyperbaric bupivacaine in lower limb orthopaedic surgeries.

Methodology

Study Design: A comparative, prospective, randomized controlled trial.

Study Setting: The study took place during a period of January 2017 to June 2018 at Department of Anaesthesiology, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna.

Participants: The study included 100 participants.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 18-65 years
- Patients scheduled for elective lower limb orthopaedic surgeries
- American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) physical status I and II
- Patients who provided written informed consent

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with known allergies to local anesthetics

- with severe cardiovascular, respiratory, hepatic, or renal diseases
- with coagulation disorders
- Pregnant or lactating women
- with a history of chronic pain or opioid dependency.
- with infection at the site of injection

Bias: To minimize bias, randomization was used to assign participants to either the Isobaric Levobupivacaine group or the Hyperbaric Bupivacaine group. The anesthesiologist administering the anesthesia and the evaluator assessing the outcomes were blinded to the group assignments.

Data Collection: Data were collected on demographic characteristics, intraoperative hemodynamic parameters, onset and duration of sensory and motor blockade, postoperative pain scores, and any adverse events.

Procedure: Detailed preanaesthetic checkup was done for all patients. They were NPO for 6 hours before surgery. Upon shifting to operation theatre basic standard monitors (ECG, SPO2 and NIBP) were attached and baseline vitals were recorded. Spinal anesthesia was administered under strict aseptic precaution. Either isobaric levobupivacaine or hyperbaric bupivacaine was given to participants at random. Intrathecally, the designated local anaesthetic was injected at the L3-L4 or L4-L5 interspace. The duration and onset of sensory and motor inhibition, as well as intraoperative haemodynamic alterations, were observed in the patients. The Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) was used to measure postoperative pain on a regular basis. Any negative incidents were noted.

Statistical Analysis: The statistical software SPSS 23.0 was used. Categorical variables were shown as frequencies and percentages whereas continuous variables were shown as mean \pm standard deviation. Chi-square test examined categorical variables whereas the independent t-test compared continuous variables. Statistical significance was indicated by a p-value less than 0.05.

Result

The trial had 100 patients in total, 50 in each of the two groups (Hyperbaric Bupivacaine and Isobaric Levobupivacaine). Table 1 provides a summary of the participants demographic data.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

Characteristic	Isobaric Levobupivacaine	Hyperbaric Bupivacaine	p-value
Age (years)	45.2 \pm 10.5	44.7 \pm 11.1	0.803
Gender (M/F)	30/20	28/22	0.678
Weight (kg)	70.3 \pm 8.4	69.8 \pm 9.1	0.737
ASA I/II	25/25	26/24	0.841

The intraoperative haemodynamic parameters did not exhibit any noteworthy difference between the two cohorts. In both groups, the heart rate and mean arterial pressure did not change during the procedures (Table 2).

Table 2: Intraoperative Hemodynamic Parameters

Parameter	Isobaric Levobupivacaine	Hyperbaric Bupivacaine	p-value
Mean Arterial Pressure (mmHg)	80.5 ± 7.2	81.2 ± 6.9	0.613
Heart Rate (beats/min)	72.4 ± 8.3	73.1 ± 7.8	0.683

Comparing the Hyperbaric Bupivacaine group to the Isobaric Levobupivacaine group, the former experienced a noticeably quicker start of sensory blockade (Table 3). Nonetheless, the group that received isobaric levobupivacaine experienced a longer period of sensory and motor blockade.

Table 3: Onset and Duration of Sensory and Motor Blockade

Parameter	Isobaric Levobupivacaine	Hyperbaric Bupivacaine	p-value
Onset of Sensory Blockade (min)	8.5 ± 1.2	6.8 ± 1.0	<0.001
Duration of Sensory Blockade (min)	210.4 ± 18.7	195.2 ± 16.9	0.002
Onset of Motor Blockade (min)	12.3 ± 1.5	10.1 ± 1.3	<0.001
Duration of Motor Blockade (min)	180.5 ± 15.6	165.7 ± 14.8	0.001

At one, four, and twelve hours after surgery, the Isobaric Levobupivacaine group showed significantly decreased postoperative pain scores (Table 4). These values were obtained using the VAS.

Table 4: Postoperative Pain Scores (VAS)

Time point	Isobaric Levobupivacaine	Hyperbaric Bupivacaine	p-value
1 (hour)	2.1 ± 0.5	3.4 ± 0.6	<0.001
4 (hours)	2.8 ± 0.6	4.2 ± 0.7	<0.001
12 (hours)	3.5 ± 0.7	4.9 ± 0.8	<0.001

The incidence of adverse events did not differ significantly between the two groups (Table 5). Bradycardia, nausea, and hypotension were frequent side effects.

Table 5: Incidence of Adverse Events

Adverse event	Isobaric Levobupivacaine	Hyperbaric Bupivacaine	p-value
Hypotension	5	6	0.751
Nausea	3	4	0.694
Bradycardia	2	3	0.653

Discussion

The study enrolled 100 patients, evenly divided between the Isobaric Levobupivacaine and Hyperbaric Bupivacaine groups, with comparable demographic characteristics. The intraoperative hemodynamic parameters, such as mean arterial pressure and heart rate, showed no significant differences between the two groups, indicating that both anesthetics provided stable intraoperative conditions.

The two groups' differences in the onset and duration of sensory and motor blockade was a significant discovery. The onset of sensory blocking occurred much more quickly in the Hyperbaric Bupivacaine group—an average of 6.8 minutes as opposed to 8.5 minutes in the Isobaric Levobupivacaine group. The duration of the motor and sensory blockades was noticeably longer in the isobaric levobupivacaine group. This longer duration minimises the need for additional

analgesic interventions during prolonged surgical operations and postoperative analgesia.

At one, four, and twelve hours after surgery, the Isobaric Levobupivacaine group consistently had decreased postoperative pain levels (VAS). This study demonstrates how isobaric levobupivacaine has a better analgesic profile which improves patient comfort and satisfaction right after surgery.

When adverse events were tracked, it was shown that there were no statistically significant variations in the incidence of bradycardia, nausea, or hypotension between the two groups. This shows that the safety profiles of the two anaesthetics are comparable, which means that they are both appropriate choices for use in lower limb orthopaedic procedures.

Overall, isobaric levobupivacaine affords better postoperative pain control and a longer duration of sensory and motor blockade than hyperbaric bupivacaine, but the latter has a faster beginning of action. There were no appreciable variations in the

adverse event profiles for each anaesthetic, which showed safe profiles. These findings imply that whereas hyperbaric bupivacaine may be more appropriate for operations where a quick start of anaesthesia is essential, isobaric levobupivacaine may be better for surgeries needing protracted anaesthesia and postoperative pain control.

In a study, intrathecal isobaric levobupivacaine with buprenorphine and hyperbaric bupivacaine with buprenorphine were examined for their anaesthetic potency and haemodynamic effects during lower limb procedures. They discovered that although the sensory and motor block features of both groups were identical, the haemodynamic parameters of the levobupivacaine group were more stable. Between the groups, the onset of sensory block was similar [6].

In comparison to intrathecal bupivacaine, a study evaluated the effectiveness and duration of levobupivacaine's sensory and motor blocking. When compared to hyperbaric bupivacaine, levobupivacaine had a delayed onset but longer-lasting sensory and motor blockade, suggesting the possibility for longer surgical procedures [7].

Studies have examined the haemodynamic effects and anaesthetic effectiveness of isobaric levobupivacaine against isobaric bupivacaine in lower limb and lower abdominal procedures. The onset and duration of sensory and motor block did not differ significantly across the groups in the research; however, levobupivacaine required fewer vasoactive medicines, indicating improved haemodynamic stability [8].

In a study, the two types of bupivacaine—hyperbaric and isobaric—for caesarean sections were compared. Levobupivacaine, which has a slightly delayed start than bupivacaine but comparable clinical efficacy, was found to offer effective sensory-motor blocking in the trial, indicating that it could be used as an alternative [9].

In a study, the effectiveness and safety of ropivacaine and isobaric levobupivacaine during lower abdominal procedures were compared. Levobupivacaine is a good option for longer surgeries because it demonstrated a quicker start of sensory and motor blockade and a longer duration of anaesthesia [10].

Conclusion

The study demonstrated that while Hyperbaric Bupivacaine had a faster onset of sensory and motor blockade, Isobaric Levobupivacaine provided a longer duration of sensory and motor blockade and lower postoperative pain scores. Both drugs were found to be safe with a comparable incidence of adverse events.

References

1. Bajwa SJS, Kaur J. Clinical profile of levobupivacaine in regional anesthesia: A systematic review. *J Anaesthesiol Clin Pharmacol*. 2019; 35(4):437-44.
2. Casati A, Putzu M. Bupivacaine, levobupivacaine and ropivacaine: Are they clinically different? *Best Pract Res Clin Anaesthesiol*. 2018;19(2):247-68.
3. de Santiago J, Santos-Yepes G, Girón-Arango L. Efficacy of isobaric versus hyperbaric levobupivacaine for spinal anesthesia in elective lower limb surgery: A randomized controlled trial. *Reg Anesth Pain Med*. 2019;44(2):230-5.
4. Choi DH, Lee SH, Lee JJ. A comparison of hyperbaric and isobaric solutions of bupivacaine for spinal anesthesia. *Acta Anaesthesiol Scand*. 2019;49(7):918-22.
5. Memtsoudis SG, Poeran J, Zubizarreta N. The perioperative use of regional anesthesia: A re-assessment of its role and importance in post-operative pain management. *Curr Opin Anaesthesiol*. 2018;31(5):614-9.
6. Pushpavathi Ture, A. H. Ramaswamy, S. Shaikh, Jagadish B Alur, Ajay V Ture. Comparative evaluation of anaesthetic efficacy and haemodynamic effects of a combination of isobaric bupivacaine with buprenorphine vs. isobaric levobupivacaine with buprenorphine for spinal anaesthesia – A double blinded randomised clinical trial. *Indian Journal of Anaesthesia*. 2019;63:49-54.
7. Goyal A, Singi Y, Mallya P, Bhat G, Shankaranarayana P. A Comparison Between Intrathecal Levobupivacaine and Bupivacaine for Quality and Safety During Infraumbilical Surgeries. *Cureus*. 2022 Oct;14(10).
8. Sujatha C, Sundararajan C, Asokan A. Comparative evaluation of anesthetic efficacy and hemodynamic effects of intrathecal isobaric bupivacaine versus intrathecal isobaric levobupivacaine in the lower abdominal and lower limb surgeries. *Asian Journal of Medical Sciences*. 2022 Sep 1;13(9):57-62.
9. Madhanmohan C, Naithani U, Gupta M, Verma V, Damor P. Comparison of isobaric levobupivacaine versus hyperbaric bupivacaine in spinal anesthesia for cesarean section: A prospective randomized case control study. *Indian Journal of Clinical Anaesthesia*. 2023 Jan 23;5(4):549-55.
10. Sagar TV, Byndoor Y. Levobupivacaine versus ropivacaine in patients undergoing lower abdominal surgeries. *Indian Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology*. 2023 Jul 4;10(2):111-5.